

A Study on Travelling Salesperson Problems

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Abstract

In this paper, graph, simple graph, directed graph, simple path, cycle, simple cycle are presented. After that Euler's cycle, Hamiltonian cycle are studied and travelling salesperson problems are solved.

1. Graph

1.1 Definition. A *graph* G is an ordered triple $(V(G), E(G), \chi_G)$ consisting of a nonempty set $V(G)$ of vertices, a set $E(G)$, disjoint from $V(G)$, of edges, and an incidence function χ_G that associates with each edge of G an unordered pair of (not necessarily distinct) vertices of G . If e is an edge and u and v are vertices such that $\chi_G(e) = uv$, then e is said to join u and v ; the vertices u and v are called the ends of e .

1.2 Example. $G = (V(G), E(G), \chi_G)$ where $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5\}$,

$E(G) = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4, e_5, e_6, e_7, e_8\}$ and χ_G is defined by

$\chi_G(e_1) = v_1v_2, \chi_G(e_2) = v_2v_3, \chi_G(e_3) = v_3v_3, \chi_G(e_4) = v_3v_4,$

$\chi_G(e_5) = v_2v_4, \chi_G(e_6) = v_4v_5, \chi_G(e_7) = v_2v_5, \chi_G(e_8) = v_2v_5$. A graph is shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1

1.3 Definition. A graph is *simple* if it has no loops and no two of its links join the same pair of vertices.

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1.4 Example. Some simple graphs are shown in Fig.2

Fig.2

1.5 Definition. A simple graph in which each pair of distinct vertices is joined by an edge is called a *complete* graph.

Some complete graphs are shown in Fig.3

Fig.3

1.6 Definition. A *directed graph* G consists of a set V of vertices (or nodes) and a set E of edges (or arcs) such that each edge $e \in E$ is associated with an ordered pair of vertices. If there is a unique edge e associated with the ordered pair (v, w) of vertices, we write $e = (v, w)$.

1.7 Example. A directed graph is shown in Fig. 4. The directed edges are indicated by arrow. Edge e_1 is associated with the ordered pair (v_2, v_1) of vertices and edge e_7 is associated with the ordered pair (v_6, v_6) of vertices. Edge e_1 is denoted (v_2, v_1) and edge e_7 is denoted (v_6, v_6) .

Fig.4

1.8 Example. In Fig.5 distinct edges e_1 and e_2 are both associated with the vertex pair. Such edges are called *parallel edges*. An edge incident on a single vertex is called a *loop*. e_3 is a loop. A vertex that is not incident on any edge is called an *isolated vertex*. v_4 is an isolated vertex.

Fig.5

2. Paths

2.1 Definition

Let v_0 and v_n be vertices in the graph. A *path* from v_0 to v_n of length n is an alternating sequence of $n + 1$ vertices and n edges beginning with vertices v_0 and ending with vertices v_n , $(v_0, e_1, v_1, e_2, v_2, \dots, v_{n-1}, e_n, v_n)$. In which edge e_i is incident on vertices v_{i-1} and v_i for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$.

Fig.6

2.2 Example

In the graph of Fig.6 $(1, e_1, 2, e_2, 3, e_3, 4, e_4, 2)$ is a path of length 4 from vertex 1 to vertex 2.

2.3 Definition

A graph with numbers on edges is called a *weighted graph*. In a weighted graph, the *length of a path* is the sum of the weights of the edges in the path.

The graph of Fig.7 is called a weighted graph. The weight of edge (c, e) is 5.

Fig.7

2.4 Definition

A graph G is *connected* if given any vertices v and w in G , there is a path from v to w .

2.5 Example

The graph G of Fig.7 is connected since any given vertices v and w in G , there is a path from v to w .

2.6 Example

The graph G of Fig.8 is not connected since for example there is no path from vertex v_2 to vertex v_5 .

Fig.8

2.7 Definition

Let v and w be vertices in a graph G . A *simple path* from v to w is a path from v to w with no repeated vertices. A *cycle* (or circuit) is a path of nonzero length from v to v with no repeated edges. A *simple cycle* is a cycle from v to v in which, except for the beginning and ending vertices that are both equal to v , there are no repeated vertices.

3. Euler Cycle

3.1 Definition

The *degree* of a vertex v , $\delta(v)$ is the number of edges incident on V .

Fig.9

$$\delta(v_1)=5, \delta(v_2)=3, \delta(v_3)=3, \delta(v_4)=1.$$

3.2 Definition

A circle in a graph G that includes all the edges and all the vertices of G is called an *Euler cycle*.

3.3 Theorem

If G is a connected graph and every vertex has even degree then G has an *Euler cycle*.

3.4 Problem

Let G be the graph of Fig.10. Use theorem to verify that G has an Euler cycle. Find an Euler cycle for G .

Fig.10

Solution

G is connected and that $\delta(v_1) = \delta(v_2) = \delta(v_3) = \delta(v_5) = 4$,

$\delta(v_4) = 6, \delta(v_6) = \delta(v_7) = 2$. Since the degree of every vertices in G is even, by the above thorem, G has an Euler cycle. The Euler cycle is

$(v_6, v_4, v_7, v_5, v_1, v_3, v_4, v_1, v_2, v_5, v_4, v_2, v_3, v_6)$.

3.5 Example

Decide whether the graph has an Euler cycle. If the graph has an Euler cycle, exhibit one.

Fig. 11

Solution

The graph G is connected and $\delta(v_3) = \delta(v_5) = \delta(v_8) = 2, \delta(v_2) = \delta(v_4) = \delta(v_6) = \delta(v_7) = 3,$

$\delta(v_1) = 4$. Since the degree of every vertex in G is not even. By Theorem (3.3), G has no Euler cycle.

4. Hamiltonian Cycle

4.1 Definition

A *Hamiltonian cycle* is a cycle in a graph G that contains each vertex in G exactly one except for the starting and ending vertex that appears twice.

4.2 Example

Fig. 12

The cycle (a, b, c, d, e, f, g, a) is a Hamiltonian cycle for the graph of above Figure.

Fig. 13

4.3 Example

Find a Hamiltonian cycle in the graph

Fig. 14

Solution

The Hamiltonian cycle is $(a, b, e, f, g, c, h, j, i, d, a)$.

Fig. 15

4.4 Theorem: If G is a simple graph with $v \geq 3$ and $\delta \geq \frac{v}{2}$, then G is Hamiltonian.

Proof : By contradiction. Suppose that the theorem is false, and let G be a maximal nonhamiltonian simple graph with $v \geq 3$ and $\delta \geq \frac{v}{2}$. Since $v \geq 3$, G cannot be complete. Let u and v be nonadjacent vertices in G . By the choice of G , $G + uv$ is Hamiltonian. Moreover, since G is nonhamiltonian, each Hamilton cycle of $G + uv$ must contain the edge uv . Thus there is a Hamilton path $v_1v_2 \dots v_v$ in G with origin $u = v_1$ and terminus $v = v_v$. Set

$$S = \{v_i/u | v_{i+1} \in E\} \text{ and } T = \{v_i/v_i | v \in E\}. \text{ Since } v_v \notin S \cup T \text{ we have}$$

$$(*) \quad |S \cup T| < v.$$

$$(**) \text{ Furthermore } |S \cap T| = 0$$

since if $S \cap T$ contained some vertex v_i , then G would have the Hamilton cycle $v_1v_2 \dots v_i, v_v v_{v-1} \dots v_{i+1}v_1$, contrary to assumption, we can see in the following figure.

Fig. 16

Using $(*)$ and $(**)$ we obtain $d(u) + d(v) = |S| + |T| = |S \cup T| + |S \cap T| < v$. But this contradicts the hypothesis that $\delta \geq \frac{v}{2}$.

4.5 Example

Show that the graph G does not contain a Hamiltonian cycle.

Fig .17

Solution

By the theorem(4.4), the graph G is not enough for Hamiltonian cycle since degree of vertex j has degree 2.

The travelling salesperson problem is related to the problem of finding a Hamiltonian cycle in a graph. The problem is: Given a weighted graph G , find a minimum-length Hamiltonian cycle in G . If we think of the vertices in a weighted graph as a cities and the edge weighted as distances, the salesperson problem is to find a shortest route in which the salesperson can visit each city one time, starting and ending at the same city.

Let us consider the following problem,

4.6 Example

Solve the travelling salesperson problem for the graph.

Fig. 18

Solution

In a minimum weight Hamiltonian cycle, every vertices have degree 2. Since degree of a is 2, we cannot include edges (a, c) and (a, e) . We must include edges (a, b) and (a, d) . Since the degree of b is 2, we cannot include edges (b, d) and (b, e) , we must include edge (b, c) . Since the degree of c is 2, we cannot include edge (c, d) and we must include edge (c, e) . Therefore the edges (a, b) , (b, c) , (c, e) , (e, d) and (d, a) include. This is a Hamiltonian cycle. Therefore (a, b, c, e, d, a) is minimal.

Fig. 19

4.7 Problem

Solve the travelling sales person for the graph. In this problem **a** represents the **BagoMyoma Market**, **b** represents the **clock tower**, **c** represents the **people’s hospital**, **d** represents the **House of parliament**, **e** represents the **Bago Region Development committee**, **f** represents **Shwemawdaw Pagoda**, **g** represents **Thiri Store**, **h** represents **Laik Pyar Lake**, **e** represents **Bago prison** and **j** represents **Bago City Development Committee**.

Fig. 20

Solution

In a minimum weight Hamiltonian cycle, every vertices have degree 2. Therefore edges (a, b) , (a, j) , (j, i) , (i, h) , (g, f) , (f, e) and (e, d) include. Since degree of h is 2, we cannot include edge (b, h) and we must include edges (h, g) and (b, c) . Since degree of g is 2, we cannot include edges (g, c) and (g, d) , we must include edge (c, d) . Therefore the edges (a, b) , (a, j) , (j, i) , (i, h) , (g, f) , (f, e) , (e, d) , (h, g) , (b, c) and (c, d) include. This is a Hamiltonian cycle. Therefore $(a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, a)$ is minimal.

Fig. 21

Conclusion

As this study did research on the shortest path, I hope it will be very helpful for travel company and salesperson when they set their paths to travel or go round.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express gratitude to Dr. Aye Aye Tun, Rector, Bago University and Pro-rector Dr. Yin Yin Than, Bago university for their permission to carry out this research. I also wish to thank Dr. Than Than Oo (Professor and Head) Department of Mathematics, Bago university for allowing this research to be carried out and giving her encouragements.

References

- J.A. Bondy and U.S.R. Murty. (1976). *Graph Theory with Applications*. New York: Elsevier Science Publishing Co., Inc.
- R. Johnsonbaugh. (1990). *Discrete Mathematics*. New York: Macmillan Publishing Company.